

Quality Assessment Process for the Study: Challenges in Constructing Deep Learning Software - A Systematic Literature Review

I. QUALITY ASSESSMENT

To minimize bias and ensure the quality of the primary studies in our SLR, we conducted a quality assessment based on the guidelines proposed by B. Kitchenham [1]. This process involved defining quality criteria that aligned with our research question and could be consistently applied to all studies, developing a scoring system to assess each study based on these criteria, and applying this system to all identified primary studies. We then interpreted the assessment results to identify any patterns or trends in the quality of the studies. In the following sections, we provide a detailed explanation of each step of the quality assessment process and present the results of our analysis.

A. Define Quality Criteria:

This section defines the quality criteria used to assess the primary studies included in our SLR. These criteria are tailored to our research question and the specific context of implementing DL software. The quality criteria are as follows:

- 1) Clarity of Research Objectives (**C1**): The study clearly states its research objectives or research questions related to the challenges faced by software developers in implementing DL software.
- 2) Appropriate Research Methodology (**C2**): The study uses a suitable research methodology (e.g., case study, experiment, survey) to investigate the challenges in implementing DL software.
- 3) Sample Representativeness (**C3**): The study includes a representative and diverse sample of software developers or projects, ensuring the findings are generalizable to the broader population of interest.
- 4) Adequate Data Collection (**C4**): The study employs rigorous and unbiased data collection methods to gather information on the challenges faced by software developers in implementing DL software.
- 5) Comprehensive Data Analysis (**C5**): The study conducts thorough data analysis, examining potential confounding factors, and appropriately addresses any limitations.
- 6) Clear Presentation of Results (**C6**): The study presents its results clearly and comprehensively, allowing readers to understand the identified challenges and their implications for DL software development.
- 7) Valid and Justifiable Conclusions (**C7**): The study's conclusions are supported by the data and analysis presented, and the implications for future research and practice in the field of DL software development are discussed.

B. Develop Scoring System:

We developed a scoring system based on the defined quality criteria to evaluate each primary study. For each criterion, we assigned a score of 0 or 1, with 0 indicating that the study did not meet the criterion and 1 indicating that the study met the criterion. The total quality score for a study can range from 0 (lowest quality) to 7 (highest quality).

C. Quality Assessment of Primary Studies:

After defining the quality criteria and developing the scoring system, we conducted a rigorous quality assessment of each primary study included in our SLR. The assessment was conducted carefully and thoroughly, consistent with the guidelines set forth by Kitchenham [1], to ensure a comprehensive and unbiased evaluation of the primary studies, contributing to the reliability and validity of our SLR findings. The scores for each quality criterion (0 or 1) were assigned to each study based on the defined quality criteria. The quality assessment results are summarized in Tables I, including the reference number of each study, the scores for each quality criterion, and the total quality score. Based on our scoring system, we decided to remove 6 studies that did not meet the minimum quality score of 4, as they were not considered reliable sources of evidence for our research question. This threshold was chosen to strike a balance between including a sufficient number of studies for analysis and maintaining the evidence's overall quality. Consequently, 43 studies were included in our SLR for further analysis, providing more robust evidence for our analysis and conclusions. The next step in the SLR process is data extraction from these selected studies. More details on the Quality Assessment analysis are available in the Data Extraction form on the Zenodo platform at [10.5281/zenodo.7913957](https://zenodo.org/record/105281/10.5281/zenodo.7913957)

REFERENCES

- [1] B.A Kitchenham & Charters, "Guidelines for performing systematic literature reviews in software engineering," Tech. report, Ver. 2.3 EBSE Tech. Report. EBSE, vol. 1, pp. 1-54, 2007.

